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ANALYSIS OF THE FEASIBILITY OF INCLUDING LIBRAS IN THE INITIAL YEARS AND ITS INCLUSION IN ENEM

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ABSTRACT

Reality is imposed by the need to provide greater social inclusion and the challenge is to understand this paradigm that is presented in national education. The universe was made up of all Libras teachers and professionals. The population includes professionals and teachers who are in Faculties of Pedagogy and Faculties of Speech and Hearing Therapy, located in the city of Caldas Novas - GO.